

DIFFERENTIAL REINFORCEMENT OF LOW RATES, CAREGIVER TRAINING, VISUAL SUPPORTS IN MANAGING AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR DUE TO ROUTINE DISRUPTIONS IN NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Comorbid disruptive behavior disorders occur in up to 80% of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Children with ASD often present as noncompliant, aggressive and inattentive making it difficult to interact in new situations, change in daily life patterns, social interaction, and engage in learning and social activities across settings. Parents and school staff report spending excessive time managing disruptive behaviors at the expense of engaging these children in meaningful skill development. Identifying effective interventions to decrease disruptive behaviors and increase positive skill development is of critical importance to improving outcomes for children with ASD. This case study presents the effectiveness of Differential Reinforcement of Low Rates (DRL), Caregiver involvement and visualization treatment modalities, an evidence-based intervention for young children with disruptive behavior, for addressing behavioral problems in a 4.5-year-old boy with ASD. Results indicate significant improvement in the child for aggressive behaviors and increased compliance with parents. Additionally, parents increased positive parenting skills, which include giving effective commands which enhance the child-parents' relationship. Treatment implications for child are discussed for ASD.

Keywords: Caregiver Training, DRL, Visual Supports and ASD.

INTRODUCTION

Theoretical and research bases for treatment

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) affects as many as 1 out of 36 children and adolescents (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2024), making ASD more prevalent in the pediatric population than many other widely known disorders, such as diabetes, cancer, or Down syndrome (Spinazzi et al., 2023), ASD is associated with severe impairments in social

interactions, communication skills (Sauer et al., 2021). American Psychiatric Association diagnostic criteria for ASD published in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition, Text Revision, 2022 is the persistent impairment in reciprocal social communication, social interaction, restricted & repetitive patterns of behaviors, interests, or activities (DSM-5-TR, 2022).

Although ASD screening and diagnostic systems have improved considerably over the years, few treatment options have been well documented for very young children with ASD. Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) is the hallmark of evidence-based treatments (EBT) available for children with ASD (Gitimoghaddam et al., 2022). ABA encompasses a range of systematic strategies to change behavior in measurable ways, with the aim of reducing problem behavior, increasing social behavior, and teaching new skills (Espinosa-Salas & Gonzalez-Arias, 2023) and the naturalistic treatment approaches emphasize parent-training techniques and child-led play, which take advantage of natural learning opportunities to improve communication and social development (Schreibman et al., 2015; McGee et al., 1999).

Across the literature base on both intensive ABA treatments and parent training for young children with ASD several key components have resulted in the most substantive developmental gains (Deb et al., 2020). These components include behavioral based intervention, parent involvement, a focus on increasing communication and adaptive skills, and implementation of intervention in the natural environment (Brookman-Fraze et al., 2009; Center for Autism and Developmental Disabilities Epidemiology, 2012).

Furthermore, differential reinforcement is a common intervention within behavior analysis in which concurrent schedules are manipulated for one or more response classes (Jessel et al., 2015) variations of this procedure have effectively increased appropriate behavior and decreased maladaptive behavior across a variety of populations (Rey & Gokey, 2023).

In addition to the above, Parent Child Interaction Therapy (PCIT) is an empirically supported and manualized parent coaching intervention that aims to increase children's positive behavior, decrease children's negative behavior, and increase parents' behavioral management skills (Lieneman et al., 2017; McNeil et al., 2010). PCIT, designed for children ages 2 to 7 years, is a behavioral intervention that uses parent management training, focusing on the parent as the agent of change, and implementing skills and strategies learned in sessions into the home setting

(Calderone et al., 2025). In the first phase of PCIT, Child Directed Interactions (CDI), parents are coached to use positive parenting strategies like; behavior descriptions, labeled praises, reflective statements, enthusiasm, and imitation (Skoranski et al., 2022) and planned ignoring to increase child's pro-social behaviors. In the second phase, Parent Directed Interactions, parents learn to give clear, effective commands followed by labeled praise for compliance or a time-out sequence for noncompliance (Monahan et al., 2018) weekly coaching, along with daily practice at home, that help parents to master an authoritative parenting style over the course of approximately twelve 1-hr treatment sessions (Holliday, 2014). Differential reinforcement of low rates has been used to reduce rates of behavior across several response topographies and populations. For example, it has been reported to reduce rapid eating (Austin & Bevan, 2011; Wright & Vollmer, 2002) and stereotypy (Singh et al., 1981) in participants with profound developmental disabilities and inappropriate question asking in primary school children with behavioral disorders (Ahmad et al., 2022). Additionally visual supports can be an effective tool for managing challenging behaviors associated with ASD. This can include things like visual schedules, social stories, or picture cards (Rutherford et al., 2019).

Case Introduction:

M K was a 4.5-year-old boy who was referred to a Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Child psychiatric ward MK, a 4.5-year-old male from a middle-class nuclear family, presented in BBH with complaints of poor eye contact, echolalia, repetitive behaviors (e.g., hand flapping), sensory issues, and delayed language skills. MK's mother had reported iron deficiency during pregnancy. MK was born via C-section and he was admitted to a child nursery for three days right after birth due to experiencing post-birth hypoxic-ischemic injury. His milestones were notably delayed. MK has been attending a special education center for the past 7 months, which indicates early intervention, which is beneficial for children with developmental delays. Special education centers typically focus on language, social skills, sensory integration, and behavior

management. MK's mother didn't report family history of ASD or other psychiatric disorders, which may suggest that MK's condition is more likely due to environmental factors or random genetic variation, rather than hereditary factors reported by the mother.

Presenting Complaints:

MK parents with the complaints of poor eye contact, distinct reactions to lights, echolalia (repeating sounds), repetitive behaviors (e.g., hand flapping), poor communication skills, delayed language development, intense reactions to minor change in environment

MK's mother also completed the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL for the Ages of 1.5-5) and scores suggested clinically significant problems on the following scales: emotionally reactive, anxious/depressed, withdrawn, aggressive behavior and attention problems. For the DSM-Oriented Scale for Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) was borderline rated by MK's mother. Finally, parent ratings on the Childhood Autism Rating Scale (CARS-II), (Schopler et al., 2010) indicated mild to moderate symptoms of the ASD. Taken together, these results combined with history, and clinical observations and evaluations resulted in a diagnosis of ASD.

Clinical Observation:

This part of the assessment typically involves direct observation of MK's behaviors, communication patterns, and responses to different stimuli. The clinical informal assessment may include: Behavior Observations: General Behavior: Observe MK for any repetitive behaviors, such as hand-flapping, rocking and self-stimulatory behaviors like fidgeting with objects or fingers, or making repetitive sounds and routine changes, such as interruptions in play or new environment. Children with ASD often have difficulty adjusting to transitions. Social skills: Observe MK's eye contact when during session. Children with ASD often have limited or inconsistent eye contact which identified in MK. Monitor MK's ability to respond to social cues (e.g., smiling, greeting, following simple requests) that was poor during session.

and his daily routine, sensory issues, frequent tantrums.

Assessment:

A comprehensive assessment was conducted by a multidisciplinary approach used in multiple settings. The psychological evaluation consisted of behavior observations; behavior rating scales, completed by parents and teacher, and a semi-structured Autism evaluation were used to assist in diagnosis and intervention planning. Portage Guide to Early Education (PGEE) was completed by MK's mother, and suggest below to poor functioning across all domains according to appropriate age.

Communication skills: Pay attention to MK's use of language. Does MK echolalia (repeat words/phrases), or does MK use meaningful speech to communicate needs and observe echolalia during session with limited response. Also, poor response to name or simple requests (e.g., "Give me the toy"). Motor Skills: Observe MK's gross motor skills (e.g., ability to run, jump, and balance) and gross motor skills compromised. Also, compromised fine motor skills, such as hand writing, picking-up objects, feeding and dressing. Sensory Sensitivities: Light Sensitivity: MK react strongly to bright lights and cover their eyes or try to avoid the light source. Also, sound sensitivity was reported. MK cover ears and seem overwhelmed by loud noises such as crying. As well as, textural sensitivities observe MK avoids certain clothing materials and certain food textures. Social Interaction: MK scary to engage and interact with other or parallel play.

Case Conceptualization:

Results of the comprehensive multidisciplinary assessment indicated that MK problem behaviors were present across multiple settings, as rated by informant, using multiple evaluation tools and techniques. MK presented with extremely disruptive behaviors across settings. PCIT, DRL and Visual support was recommended as part of the intervention plan because of the considerable body of literature suggesting that it is an efficacious treatment for young children with disruptive behavior disorders and developmental disabilities (Zisser

& Eyberg, 2010). MK's Mother reported that he was motivated by their attention at times and enjoyed playing with them when he was not having a temper tantrum or engaging in self-stimulatory behavior. The entire family was overwhelmed with MK's behaviors and the degree to which they disrupted family routines and rituals, and voiced readiness to commit to intensive therapy. Due to the aggressive nature of some of MK's behaviors, as well as emotional lability and management was also an integral part of his treatment. Also, Differential reinforcement of low rates of behavior (DRL) was used as a schedule in which a minimum amount of time must elapse between responses in order for reinforcement to occur and Visual supports was presented in the form of pictures or objects. The schedule utilizes the presence of

these visuals in order to communicate clearly and concretely when events and activities will take place.

Access and Barriers to Care:

Therapy consent was taken from Mother and briefly explained therapy duration, session secluded, duration and limitations. As sessions were held late on a Monday afternoon, MK's mother and father were able to organize their work commitments to attend weekly PCIT sessions. In Govt. treatment no cost of treatment and the family had reliable transportation to clinic, which was within a reasonable distance from their home, work and cost. No other access issues or barriers to care were identified.

Treatment Implications of the Case Recommendations to Clinicians and Students

MK's and his parents attended weekly 1-hr PCIT sessions for a total of 12 weeks. Two of the 12 sessions were "teach sessions" during which MK's parents learned the core skills of In the Child Directed Interactions (CDI) and Parent Directed Interactions (PDI), without MK present. In the CDI teach session, MK's parents were taught to allow MK to lead during the "special play" time and to attend to his positive behaviors, using behavioral descriptions (e.g., you are stacking the blocks) and reflections (e.g., you said it's a blue block). Parents were instructed to practice these skills at home during 5-min "play" activities, as consistent use of these core skills promote warmer parent child interactions and secure attachment as well as increase child self-esteem and prosocial play behaviors (Campbell et al.,2023). In cases of minor inappropriate behaviors (e.g., sassiness, whining), parents were taught to use planned

ignoring, and for behaviors that could not be ignored (e.g., aggressive and destructive behaviors), parents were instructed to immediately stop the play and try again the next day. In addition, parents were taught to avoid giving commands, asking questions, or criticizing MK's behavior as these responses take over the child's lead during play, reduce child compliance, as well as impact the warmth of the parent child interaction. Homework was assigned each week to engage in daily special time and to practice CDI skills. During CDI sessions, the therapists used the PCIT manual to coach parents in the use of CDI skills via in person observation both parents' CDI skills were documented during the first 5 min of each session.

Once both parents achieved CDI mastery, defined as 10 behavioral descriptions, 10 reflections, and 10 labeled praises coded within the 5-min observation, they advanced into the PDI phase. During PDI, MK's parents were

taught effective discipline strategies, specifically how to give effective commands and how to implement DRL, Visual procedure for child noncompliance. Effective commands are specific, direct (e.g., absolutely clear that the child is being told not asked), positively stated (e.g., what to do instead of what not to do), and developmentally appropriate so that the child understands what is expected and is given the opportunity to comply. During the PDI teach session, the therapists modeled effective commands for MK's parents and then allowed them to practice and receive feedback. In the early stages of PDI, MK's parents only implemented the disciplinary strategies during special play time and as they gained confidence and demonstrated correct implementation of PDI skills, the commands and disciplinary procedures were generalized in a step-by-step process to a clean-up scenario following special play, during daily routines, the establishment of house rules, and eventually in public settings. Parents demonstrate mastery of PDI skills when 75% of commands are direct; commands are followed by labeled praises for child compliance; and the command-discipline procedure is followed for child noncompliance. Furthermore, according to MK's parents, PDI was somewhat

effective with MK when implemented in the home initially. Early on, his parents had difficulty following the DRL sequence due to MK's intense disruptive behaviors minor change in his daily routine. Consequently, the PCIT protocol of ignoring all inappropriate behavior was violated and MK did obtain parental attention for misbehavior and therapists worked with parents to address this issue and eventually his parents were able to remove everything to prevent him from hurting himself. This relieved the parents from feeling like they needed to cure for him, and consequently, resulted in their ignoring all inappropriate behaviors, which decreased the need to use the DRL and increased compliance overall. During PDI Sessions 3 and 4, two House Rules were introduced to address continued aggression and inappropriate behavior.

Interestingly, MK's parents rated his behavior as only slightly elevated for intensity and problems from the initiation of treatment despite qualitative reports of extremely disruptive behaviors (see CBCL pre and post assessment table). Parent ratings on the CBCL decreased over the course of treatment. During a 3-month post assessment, MK's mother's CBCL ratings were elevated.

Emotional/Reactive	Anxious/depressed	Somatic complaints	Withdrawn	Sleep problems	Attention Problems	Aggressive behavior
Disturbed By change	Clings	Aches	Acts to young	Doesn't want to sleep alone	Can't Concentmte	Can't stand waiting
Twitches	Feelings hurt	Cant standing without	Avoid eye contact	Trouble sleeping	Can't sit still	Defiant
Panics Shifts Between Sad-Excite	Upset by sep Look unhappy	Constipated Diarrhea	Doesn't answer Refuse active games	Nightmares Resists bed	Clumsy Quickly shift	Demands met Destroy others
Moody	Nervous	Doesn't eat well	Unresponsive to affections	Sleep little	Wanders away	Disobedient
Sulks	Self-conscious	Nausea	Little affection	Talks can in sleep		Lacks guilt
Upset By New Whining Worries	Fearful Sad	Headaches Painful B.M Stomach aches Too concerned w. neat/clean Vomits	Little interest Withdrawn	Wakes often		Easily frustrated Fights Hits other Hurts accidentally Angry mood Attacks people Punishment doesn't change Scream Selfish Stubborn Tempered

Uncooperative
 Wants attention

CBCL/11½-5 Empirically Based Scales for Boys and Girls

• **Pre assessment**

Pre-assessment: before to start intervention CBCL were administer. Post assessment: after three months intervention CBCL were administer.

Results

Results shows improvements in emotional reaction, withdrawn from situations and aggressive behavior. Also, in attention problems table show miner improvement after three months intervention.

Complicating Factors: Over the course of treatment, a few factors complicated implementation of PCIT strategies. First, MK was not responding well to new medications, and during the course of PCIT, his medication was changed three times. Second, at the initiation of PCIT, MK had weekly visits with pediatric psychiatry that could be contributing to his aggressive and atypical behaviors. In addition, two of the first three PCIT sessions were essentially stopped before coaching even began due to MK's aggressive behaviors due to frequently disruption in routine, in clinic room, thus causing more stress and frustration for the parents. Third, counseled them to continue practicing their CDI skills during daily at home. Contact was maintained with the family throughout the week to support them through this difficult time. Once DRL successfully applied, the parents reported that it was very

effective at reducing disruptive behaviors. Finally, another complicating factor that interfered with

• **Post assessment**

MK's generalization of new skills across settings.

Access and Barriers to Care

As sessions were held in Govt. hospital which is free of cost and in second half, MK's mother and father were able to organize their work commitments to attend weekly PCIT sessions and the family had reliable transportation to the clinic, which was within a reasonable distance from their home. MK's psychiatrist and PCIT therapists were in same place and in close contact. No other access issues or barriers to care were identified.

Treatment Implications of the Case

This case study described the use of PCIT, DRL & Visual support, an empirically supported intervention, to reduce disruptive and aggressive behaviors due to daily routine disruption in a young child with ASD. The course of treatment, however, provided us with new clinical challenges, which were likely associated with MK's ASD. First, MK's aggressive behavior made it challenging to complete an entire coaching session at the start of treatment, which caused MK's parents to doubt whether the appropriate intervention had been selected. However, continued practice at home was encouraged and eventually MK's behavior improved. Building

warm, positive interactions between parent and child, which is the focus of CDI, is critical to early childhood development. Through these interactions, children learn to trust their parents and accept their limits. All the while, parents learn to provide positive attention to shape their child's prosocial behaviors and to use effective discipline strategies to eliminate disruptive behaviors. In MK's case, his parents learned to give very effective commands, which were clear, developmentally appropriate, and reasonable. As such, MK quickly started to accept limits and reduce the frequency and intensity of his noncompliance and behavioral outbursts, all important skills for a child with ASD. Allowing additional time to build rapport was very important in this case. At the initiation of each session, more than the usual 5 min was allotted to build rapport with the family by discussing their current concerns with MK.

Recommendations to Clinicians and Students

Clinicians using PCIT, DRL and Visual support with children who have ASD will find that this subgroup of children can benefit greatly from basic behavior management skills. Many families of children with ASD and comorbid disruptive behaviors are overwhelmed by their child's needs and may require more clinical time than a child without ASD. We found that providing a little additional time before, after, and in between our sessions was helpful for building rapport, supporting the family, and assisting with concerns related to community, and home routines. As previously mentioned, while restricted interests are often viewed as problematic among children with ASD, these interests can serve as a starting ground for engaging a child in joint play with caregivers, during which they will learn important social skills needed for future social interactions. Finally, clinicians may need to explore ways to engage school personnel in the intervention strategies so that the child is receiving consistent messages across settings regarding appropriate and inappropriate behaviors. Teacher Child Interaction Therapy, or TCIT, is a school-based intervention, which uses the disciplinary techniques of PCIT to assist teachers with managing difficult student and classrooms. TCIT is effective for reducing disruptive and aggressive behavior while improving student

compliance (McIntosh, Rizza, & Bliss, 2000). In this case, although MK's behaviors improved considerably in the home setting, these improvements did not generalize to the classroom. Thus, for children with ASD and other severely disruptive behavior disorders, involving the school from the outset of treatment is warranted.

A couple of limitations:

are worthy of mention. First, MK was taking medications throughout the course of treatment. Therefore, we cannot be certain that behavioral improvements were solely associated with the PCIT intervention. Another limitation is the limited assessment tools used prior to and post intervention. This case study provides further evidence for the effectiveness of PCIT, DRL and visual support in managing disruptive behaviors among young children with ASD. Similar to the findings of Armstrong & Kimonis (2013), PCIT was effective in reducing behavioral outbursts, aggression, and repetitive motor behaviors in a young child with ASD. Further research on PCIT and other manualized behavioral interventions is needed to advance our understanding of the best approaches to address the disruptive behaviors associated with ASD in early childhood.

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